

ORGANIC FUNGICIDES. PART III. ON CERTAIN HIGHER ETHERS OF CRESOTINIC ESTERS

BY A. B. SEN AND K. C. JOSHI

Several higher ether-esters of cresotinic acids have been prepared preliminary to evaluation of their fungicidal activity.

The relation between the size of the molecule and its toxicity to fungi has been studied by various workers in several series of organic compounds. Baechler (*Amer. Wood-Pres. Assoc.*, 1939, **35**, 1) found that in open-chain alcohols, the potency increased with the length of the chain up to 11 carbon atoms. Kiesel (*Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1913, **27**, 391) observed that, as in alcohols, the potency of fatty acids increased with the length of the chain and maximum potency was reached at 10 to 12 carbon atoms and then decreased. In the case of aromatic compounds (Horsefall, "Organic Fungicides", p. 150), if the benzene ring is added to some other organic compound so as to bring the total number of carbon atoms closer to 12, toxicity is increased but if the number is much above 12, it decreases. Further work by Bateman (*Amer. Wood-Pres. Assoc.*, 1922, **18**, 70) and Tattersfield and Gimmingham (*Ann. Appl. Biol.*, 1928, **15**, 331) also indicates that a marked change in potency takes place in the neighbourhood of 12 carbon atoms. In continuation of our work on ethers of cresotinic esters, reported earlier (this *Journal*, 1949, **26**, 335), we have now prepared several higher ethers containing 14 to 17 carbon atoms with a view to studying the change in their toxicity to fungi.

The method used for the preparation of the ethers was as reported earlier (*loc. cit.*) viz., by refluxing the sodium derivative of the hydroxy-esters with the appropriate alkyl bromide in absolute alcohol.

EXPERIMENTAL

The two esters of *p*-cresotinic acid, 2-oxy-5-methyl methylbenzoate and 2-oxy-5-methyl ethylbenzoate, were obtained by Fischer's method by refluxing the acid with the requisite alcohol in presence of 3% hydrochloric acid gas. Their boiling points are in agreement with those reported by Pinner. (*Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 2939).

Esters of o- and m-cresotinic acids were prepared by methods already reported earlier (*loc. cit.*).

Ether-esters of cresotinic acids were prepared by refluxing the sodium salt of the cresotinic acid-alkyl ester with the required alkyl bromide (20% in excess) in absolute alcohol and extracted as reported earlier (*loc. cit.*).

The following ether-esters have been obtained.

TABLE I

C denotes crezoticinic acid.

Compounds	B. p.	Yield.	Mol. formula.	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Amyl ether of <i>o</i> -C-isopropyl ester	160°/10 mm.	42.8%	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃	72.18	72.72	9.21	9.09
Amyl ether of <i>o</i> -C-butyl ester	160°/4	41.4	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₃	73.12	73.38	9.54	9.35
Hexyl ether of <i>o</i> -C-butyl ester	116°/5	46.2	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₃	73.33	73.97	9.62	9.58
Amyl ether of <i>m</i> -C-methyl ester	150°/5	33.3	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₃	70.92	71.18	8.52	8.47
Amyl ether of <i>p</i> -C-methyl ester	175°/6	62.5	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₃	70.89	71.18	8.55	8.47
Hexyl ether of <i>p</i> -C-methyl ester	134°/4	50.0	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃	71.56	72.00	9.00	8.80
Amyl ether of <i>p</i> -C-ethyl ester	176°/4	45.4	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃	71.63	72.00	8.91	8.80
Hexyl ether of <i>p</i> -C-ethyl ester	122°/4	56.8	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃	72.39	72.72	9.14	9.09
<i>iso</i> Amyl ether of <i>p</i> -C-ethyl ester.	186°/6	60.0	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₃	71.85	72.00	8.96	8.80

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

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